

The Frequency Of Empyema/Gangrene In Acute Cholecystitis And Its Relationship With Gender

Saniya Ahmed¹, Rabia binte-Iftikhar¹, Mehreen Fatima²

¹ Student, 4th year MBBS, Rawalpindi Medical University.

² Demonstrator, Pathology Department, Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi.

Abstract

Background: Cholecystectomy is one of the most frequently performed surgical procedures across the globe and is considered as a treatment of choice for majority cases of acute cholecystitis. Empyema/gangrene is one of the most frequent and important complication of acute cholecystitis. World over, the association between gender and the complications associated with acute cholecystitis is poorly documented. The purpose of the study was to find out the frequency of empyema/gangrene in acute cholecystitis and to determine its relation with gender.

Methods: This cross-sectional descriptive study, was conducted at histopathology laboratory, Department of Pathology, Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, by reviewing past medical record of (2016) of 76 patients (38 males and 38 females) of acute cholecystitis selected on the basis of non-probability consecutive sampling. Data was analysed using SPSS 23.

Results: Out of 76 patients, 25(32.9%) patients of acute cholecystitis developed empyema/gangrene. Out of 38 males, 17(45%) developed empyema/gangrene as a complication whereas out of 38 females only 8(21%) developed empyema/gangrene. A statistically significant portion of male patients developed empyema/gangrene, [p=0.028].

Conclusion: Male gender has a statistically significant relationship of developing empyema/gangrene in acute cholecystitis. This may help in prioritizing the patients for surgery.

Keywords: Bladder, Male gender.

Introduction

Acute cholecystitis is the acute inflammation of the gall bladder, which is most commonly caused by gall stones [1]. Gall stones affect about 10% of the western population [2]. Asymptomatic gall stones are present in more than 80% of the patients and among the patients

of symptomatic gall stones only 1-3% develop acute cholecystitis.^{1,3} Hence acute cholecystitis is considered the most common severe complication of gall stones.³ Ascariasis, a major cause of biliary disease also results in acute cholecystitis because the cystic duct obstruction caused by the helminth causes an inflammatory process to start.⁴

Acute cholecystitis is diagnosed on the basis of clinical features and ultrasonography.¹ Literature gives two opinions regarding the surgical treatment of acute cholecystitis- first is the early surgery within few days of onset and second is delayed operation after subsidence of acute symptoms.⁵ Laparoscopic cholecystectomy was initially contraindicated in patients of acute cholecystitis⁶, but now it is considered to be the most reliable and safest surgery for acute cholecystitis and is the treatment of choice.⁷ Demand of cholecystectomy has surpassed the capacity of available resources in public hospitals and patients have to wait for definitive treatment which poses a risk for development of complications. So patients should be prioritized for surgery according to the risk of developing complications.⁸

This wait or delay in surgery in acute cases leads to worsening of inflammatory processes and bacterial colonization, hence predisposing to life threatening conditions of gangrenous and empyematous cholecystitis if left untreated.⁹ Clinical diagnosis to differentiate between complicated (empyema/gangrene) and uncomplicated acute cholecystitis is difficult because the clinical features are the same such as biliary colic,¹⁰ and only one-third of gangrenous gall bladder patients show positive Murphy's sign probably due to necrotic denervation [11]. Empyema and gangrene can further cause complications such as biliary peritonitis, fistula, and intra peritoneal abscess formation.¹²⁻¹⁴ As Higher morbidity is associated with laproscopic cholecystectomy of gangrenous and empyematous gall bladder, so to prevent this complication early cholecystectomy is recommended i.e. it should be

performed before the appearance of these complications.¹⁵

World over the association between gender and the complications associated with acute cholecystitis is poorly documented.¹⁶ Hence there is a need to conduct studies in order to identify the risk factors for the development of complications in acute cholecystitis.

To the best of our knowledge, no previous research on this topic has been done in our study setting. This study particularly aims to find association of a particular gender with severity of inflammation as predicted by frequency of empyema/gangrene in patients of acute cholecystitis. If a statistically significant association for suspicion of empyema/gangrene is developed in any of the two genders, it will indicate tendency of patients of that gender to develop cholecystitis of greater severity and hence will be prone to develop complications. Moreover it will help in stratifying patients for surgery and council them accordingly.

Materials and Methods

The cross-sectional retrospective study, was conducted at histopathology laboratory, Department of Pathology, Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, by reviewing past medical record of (2016) of 76 patients (38 males and 38 females) of acute cholecystitis selected on the basis of non-probability consecutive sampling. Sample size was calculated using WHO sample size calculator, with 95% confidence interval and 5% margin of error. Information regarding, laboratory ID number, gender, age and histopathological findings of patients were recorded on a proforma. Empyema of gallbladder was noted on the basis of operative findings whereas gangrenous gallbladder was noted as per histopathology report and also operative finding. Data was analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences, SPSS Version 23. Hypothesis was tested by applying Chi square test reported as significant with $p < 0.05$. Frequencies and percentages were presented using descriptive statistics. Results of males and females were compared.

Results:

76 cases (38 males and 38 females) which fulfilled the inclusion criteria were reviewed.

Acute cholecystitis complication in the form of empyema/gangrene was recorded in 25(32.9%) patients. Frequency of empyema/gangrene was more in male patients than females as shown in table I. Age ranges and mean ages of males and females are also

compared in table I. Chi square test of independence was applied comparing the frequency of empyema/gangrene in males and females. A significant interaction was found $\chi^2 (1, N = 76) = 4.828$, $p = 0.028$.

Co-relation of empyema/gangrene with respect to the age groups is shown in figure 1.

Table I Relation of gender with incidence of complication and age

Gender	Empyema/gangrene Present n(%)	Empyema/gangrene Absent n(%)	Min.-Max age (yrs)	Mean age (yrs)
Males	17(45)	21(55)	10-85	47.47
Females	8(21)	30(79)	23-75	43.16

Fig I: Relation Of Age With Frequency Of Empyema

Discussion:

This study was done to assess whether the frequency of empyema/gangrene is more in males presenting with acute cholecystitis. Testing our hypothesis by applying chi square test of independence, male gender was confirmed as a risk for developing empyema/gangrene.

Our study results showed that empyema/gangrene of gallbladder was present in 45% of males as compared to only 21% of females. Males and females were comparable with regard to age. p value of 0.028 proves a statistically significant relation of male gender with the risk of empyema/gangrene in acute cholecystitis. In a local study Muhammad Laiq-uz-Zaman khan concluded that empyema/gangrene was present in 48% of male patients and only 24% of female patients.⁸ In another international study, Peter C Ambe reported extensive gallbladder inflammation

in males and females as 62.31% and 30.43%, $p=0.002$ respectively.¹⁷ Both these results are in favour of our study. Our study results are more in coherence with the results of local study⁸ than an international study due to comparable hospital settings, environmental factors and patients' literacy rate in local study population.

The reason for the male gender to be at more risk for developing empyema/gangrene is not well understood, however various biological, anatomical and psychological reasons have been proposed. Male patients have a higher threshold of pain, for this reason they might have some episodes of undiagnosed cholecystitis predisposing to complications of acute cholecystitis.¹⁷ As females are more sensitized due to hormonal differences, they seek medical help more often than males.⁸ Moreover difference in the fat percentage and size of peritoneal cavity affect the clinical presentation of cholecystitis.¹⁶

Presence of empyema/gangrene indicates the severity of inflammation. Inflammation, adhesions and anatomic difficulties are considered as the main causes for conversion from a laparoscopic to open cholecystectomy. Among these causes only inflammation differs significantly with gender [16]. Hence male gender increases the conversion rate to open cholecystectomy and increases the risk for possible complications of surgery.⁸ An increased incidence of morbidity, longer operative time & prolong post-operative hospital stay is reported in males than females.¹⁶ So patients' pre-operative status should be evaluated and classified into groups on the basis of severity of inflammation. We should prioritize male patients who are at risk of developing empyema/gangrene, so as to prevent further pre-operative and post-operative complications.

Limitation of this study is that it is single centered. There is a need to do further researches to find out more predictors along with their reasons for the complication of acute cholecystitis, so that prevention, early diagnosis of complications and prioritization of patients can be done.

Conclusion:

Male gender has a statistically significant relationship for developing empyema/gangrene in acute cholecystitis. This may help in prioritizing the patients for surgery.

Acknowledgments:

I am grateful to the Almighty God whose blessings made this tedious job easy. Secondly I'm thankful to my parents for their unconditional support. I would like to pay special regards to Dr. Faiza Aslam, Dr. Omera Shuaib and Dr. Muneeba Faisal for their worthy guidance and advise.

References:

1. Indar AA, Beckingham IJ. Acute cholecystitis. *BMJ* 2002;325(7365):639-43.
2. Jensen KH, Jorgensen T. Incidence of gallstones in a Danish population. *Gastroenterology* 1991;100(3):790-4.
3. Friedman GD. Natural history of asymptomatic and symptomatic gallstones. *AmJSurg* 1993;165(4):399-404.
4. Khuroo MS. Ascariasis. *Gastroenterol Clin North Am* 1996;25:553-77.
5. Järvinen HJ, Hästbacka J. Early Cholecystectomy for Acute Cholecystitis: A Prospective Randomized Study. *Ann Surg* 1980;191(4):501-5.
6. Cuschieri A, Dubois F, Mouiel J, Mouret P, Becker H, Buess G, et al. The European experience with laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Am J Surg* 1991;161(3):385-7.
7. Gharaibeh K, Qasaimeh G, Al-Heiss H, Ammari F, Bani-Hani K, Al-Jaberi T et al. Effect of Timing of Surgery, Type of Inflammation, and Sex on Outcome of Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy for Acute Cholecystitis. *J Laparoendosc Adv Surg Tech A* 2002;12(3):193-8.
8. Khan ML, Abbasi MR, Jawed M, Shaikh U. Male gender and sonographic gall bladder wall thickness: important predictable factors for empyema and gangrene in acute cholecystitis. *J Pak Med Assoc* 2014;64(2):159-62.
9. Borzellino G1, Sauerland S, Minicozzi AM, Verlato G, Di Pietrantonj C, de Manzoni G, et al. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy for severe acute cholecystitis. A meta-analysis of results. *Surg Endosc* 2008;22(1):8-15.
10. Yacoub WN, Petrosyan M, Sehgal I, Ma Y, Chandrasoma P, Mason RJ. Prediction of patients with acute cholecystitis requiring emergent cholecystectomy: a simple score. *Gastroenterol Res Pract* 2010;2010:1-5.
11. Simeone JF, Brink JA, Mueller PR, Compton C, Hahn PF, Saini S, et al. The sonographic diagnosis of acute gangrenous cholecystitis: Importance of the Murphy sign. *AJR Am J Roentgenol* 1989;152(2):289-90.
12. Merriam LT, Kanaan SA, Dawes LG, Angelos P, Prystowsky JB, Rege RV, et al. Gangrenous cholecystitis: analysis of risk factors and experience with laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Surgery* 1999;126(4):680-6.
13. Corr P. Sonography of gangrenous cholecystitis. *J Emerg Trauma Shock* 2012;5(1):82-3.
14. Hunt DR, Chu FC. Gangrenous cholecystitis in the laparoscopic era. *Aust N Z J Surg* 2000;70(6):428-30.
15. Schafer M, Krahenbuhl L, Buchler MW. Predictive factors for the type of surgery in acute cholecystitis. *Am J Surg* 2001;182(3):291-7.
16. Botaitis S, Polychronidis A, Pitiakoudis M, Perente S, Simopoulos C. Does gender affect laparoscopic cholecystectomy? *Surg Laparosc Endosc Percutan Tech* 2008;18(2):157-61.
17. Ambe PC, Weber SA, Wassenberg D. Is gallbladder inflammation more severe in male patients presenting with acute cholecystitis? *BMC surgery* 2015;15(1):48.